

BENZYLTHIOUREAS. PART IV

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Several *N'*-benzyl-*N''*-aryl/2-biphenyl/2-thiazolyl/2-thiazolynyl/2-pyridyl- and β -hydroxyethyl-thioureas have been prepared.

Aryl ureas and thioureas are known to exhibit bacteriostatic activity (Beaver *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 1236; Buu-Hoi *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2815; Doub *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 2205). Important bacteriostats contain thiazole and pyridine rings. Some thiazoline derivatives also exhibit bacteriostatic activity (Cardener *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 976; Mizzoni *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 3471). 2-Biphenylthiourea exhibits the same order of toxicity to rats as α -naphthylthiourea (U.S. Patent 2,390,848; *Chem. Abs.*, 1946, 40, 1966). Several benzylthioureas also show bacteriostatic and fungitoxic activity (Trivedi *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 423; 1958, 35, 657; McKay *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 4328).

Thus we found it of considerable interest to study thioureas containing aryl, hetero, and other groups in addition to a substituted benzyl group. We have prepared the following types of unsymmetrical thioureas by the action of appropriate amine on substituted benzyl isothiocyanates:

(a)	<i>N'</i> -	(subst.)	-benzyl- <i>N''</i> -aryl-	thioureas	Table I
(b)	<i>N'</i>	..	.. <i>N''</i> (2-pyridyl)-	..	II
(c)	<i>N'</i>	..	.. <i>N''</i> (2-thiazolynyl)-	..	III
(d)	<i>N'</i>	..	.. <i>N''</i> (2-thiazolyl)-	..	IV
(e)	<i>N'</i>	..	.. <i>N''</i> (2-biphenyl)-	..	V
(f)	<i>N'</i>	..	.. <i>N''</i> (β -hydroxyethyl)-	..	VI

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Aminothiazoline was prepared from monoethanolamine by the method of Raiziss and Clemence (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3125). 2-Aminothiazole and 2-aminopyridine were of Eastman's practical grade. Substituted benzyl isothiocyanates were prepared as described previously (Trivedi *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Unsymmetrical thioureas were prepared by the action of appropriate amines on substituted benzyl isothiocyanates in ethanolic solution as described previously (*loc. cit.*). Thioureas were crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE I

Compounds. (R=)	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		Compounds. (R=)	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.				Found.	Calc.
		X=H.					X= <i>o</i> -Cl		
<i>o</i> -Cl	113°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ ClS	11.7	11.6	H	176°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ ClS	11.8	11.6
<i>m</i> -Cl	117°	"	11.4	11.6	<i>o</i> -Cl	130°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	10.5	10.3
<i>p</i> -Cl	118°	"	11.8	11.6	<i>m</i> -Cl	158°	"	10.2	10.3
<i>o</i> -Br	143°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ BrS	10.2	10.0	<i>p</i> -Cl	175°	"	10.4	10.3
<i>m</i> -Br	118°	"	9.8	10.0	<i>o</i> -Br	132°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ ClBrS	9.2	9.0
<i>p</i> -Br	132°	"	10.3	10.0	<i>m</i> -Br	130°	"	9.3	9.0
<i>o</i> -Me	131°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ S	12.3	12.5	<i>p</i> -Br	162°	"	8.9	9.0
<i>m</i> -Me	116°	"	12.7	12.5	<i>o</i> -Me	183°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ ClS	11.1	11.0
<i>p</i> -Me	120°	"	12.6	12.5	<i>m</i> -Me	117°	"	11.3	11.0
<i>o</i> -OMe	140°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ON ₂ S	11.9	11.8	<i>p</i> -Me	142°	"	10.8	11.0
					<i>o</i> -OMe	153°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ON ₂ ClS	10.2	10.4
					<i>p</i> -OMe	170°	"	10.6	10.4

TABLE I (contd.)

Compounds. (R=)	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		Compounds. (R=)	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.				Found.	Calc.
		X= <i>m</i> -Cl					X= <i>o</i> -Me.		
H	91°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ S	11.7	11.6	H	189°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	12.6	12.5
<i>o</i> -Cl	80°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	10.5	10.3	<i>o</i> -Cl	174°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ CIS	11.2	11.0
<i>m</i> -Cl	85°	"	10.4	10.3	<i>m</i> -Cl	136°	"	11.1	11.0
<i>p</i> -Cl	125°	"	10.2	10.3	<i>p</i> -Cl	148°	"	11.0	11.0
<i>p</i> -Br	126°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ ClBrS	9.2	9.0	<i>p</i> -Br	166°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ BrS	9.7	9.6
<i>o</i> -Me	93°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ CIS	11.1	11.0	<i>o</i> -Me	196°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	12.0	11.9
<i>m</i> -Me	118°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ CIS	11.2	11.0	<i>m</i> -Me	140°	"	11.7	11.9
<i>p</i> -Me	95°	"	10.9	11.0	<i>p</i> -Me	138°	"	11.8	11.9
<i>o</i> -OMe	151°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ ON ₂ CIS	10.5	10.4	<i>o</i> -OMe	144°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	11.3	11.2
<i>p</i> -OMe	183°	"	10.6	10.4	<i>p</i> -OMe	160°	"	11.1	11.2
		X= <i>p</i> -Cl.					X= <i>p</i> -Me.		
H	136°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ CIS	11.7	11.6	H	131°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	12.7	12.5
<i>o</i> -Cl	142°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	10.2	10.3	<i>o</i> -Cl	114°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ CIS	11.2	11.0
<i>m</i> -Cl	146°	"	10.5	10.3	<i>m</i> -Cl	120°	"	10.9	11.0
<i>p</i> -Cl	185°	"	10.4	10.3	<i>p</i> -Cl	174°	"	11.1	11.0
<i>o</i> -Br	161°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ ClBrS	9.2	9.0	<i>p</i> -Br	179°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ BrS	9.8	9.6
<i>m</i> -Br	164°	"	8.8	9.0	<i>o</i> -Me	107°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	12.0	11.9
<i>p</i> -Br	182°	"	9.3	9.0	<i>m</i> -Me	129°	"	12.1	11.9
<i>o</i> -Me	118°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ CIS	11.3	11.0	<i>p</i> -Me	124°	"	11.8	11.9
<i>m</i> -Me	145°	"	10.9	11.0	<i>o</i> -OMe	129°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	11.3	11.2
<i>p</i> -Me	162°	"	11.2	11.0	<i>p</i> -OMe	138°	"	11.4	11.2
<i>o</i> -OMe	140°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ ON ₂ CIS	10.5	10.3			X=2:5-Me ₂ .		
<i>p</i> -OMe	132°	"	10.4	10.3	H	141°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	12.0	11.9
		X= <i>p</i> -Br.			<i>o</i> -Cl	150°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ CIS	10.6	10.5
H	142°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ BrS	10.2	10.0	<i>m</i> -Cl	130°	"	10.4	10.5
<i>o</i> -Cl	149°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ ClBrS	9.1	9.0	<i>p</i> -Cl	157°	"	10.7	10.5
<i>m</i> -Cl	95°	"	8.9	9.0	<i>p</i> -Br	152°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ BrS	9.3	9.2
<i>p</i> -Cl	185°	"	9.0	9.0	<i>o</i> -Me	117°	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₂ S	11.5	11.3
<i>p</i> -Br	186°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ Br ₂ S	8.2	8.0	<i>m</i> -Me	99°	"	11.4	11.3
<i>o</i> -Me	139°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ BrS	9.7	9.6	<i>p</i> -Me	142°	"	11.2	11.3
<i>m</i> -Me	95°	"	9.5	9.6	<i>o</i> -OMe	112°	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ ON ₂ S	10.8	10.7
<i>p</i> -Me	157°	"	9.8	9.6	<i>p</i> -OMe	137°	"	10.9	10.7
<i>o</i> -OMe	145°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ ON ₂ BrS	9.3	9.1					
<i>p</i> -OMe	124°	"	9.2	9.1					

TABLE II

No.	Compounds. (R=)	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	H	165°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ S	13.3	13.2
2.	<i>o</i> -Cl	174°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ ClS	11.6	11.5
3.	<i>m</i> -Cl	126°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ ClS	11.3	11.5
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	179°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ ClS	11.7	11.5
5.	<i>o</i> -Br	186°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ BrS	10.1	10.0
6.	<i>m</i> -Br	128°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ BrS	9.9	10.0
7.	<i>p</i> -Br	176°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ BrS	10.2	10.0
8.	<i>o</i> -Me	174°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ S	12.7	12.5
9.	<i>m</i> -Me	97°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ S	12.4	12.5
10.	<i>p</i> -Me	184°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ S	12.6	12.5
11.	2:4-Me ₂	167°	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ S	11.9	11.8
12.	2:5-Me ₂	158°	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ S	12.0	11.8

TABLE III

No.	Compounds. (R=)	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	H	90°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂	25.4	25.5
2.	<i>o</i> -Cl	115°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ ClS ₂	22.6	22.4
3.	<i>p</i> -Cl	98°	..	22.3	22.4
4.	<i>o</i> -Me	176°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂	24.4	24.2
5.	<i>m</i> -Me	133°	..	24.0	24.2
6.	<i>p</i> -Me	130°	..	24.1	24.2
7.	3:4-Me ₂	138°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂	23.0	23.0
8.	2:4-Me ₂	169°	..	23.2	23.0
9.	2:5-Me ₂	168°	..	22.7	23.0

TABLE IV

No.	Compounds. (R=)	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	H	164°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	25.9	25.7
2.	<i>o</i> -Cl	195°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₃ ClS ₂	22.4	22.6
3.	<i>p</i> -Cl	183°	..	22.8	22.6
4.	<i>p</i> -Br.	179°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₃ BrS ₂	19.7	19.5
5.	<i>m</i> -Me	127°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	24.5	24.3
6.	<i>p</i> -Me	155°	..	24.2	24.3
7.	2:5-Me ₂	174°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	23.3	23.1

TABLE V

No.	Compounds. (R=)	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	H	112°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ S	10.2	10.1
2.	<i>o</i> -Cl	140°	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ ClS	9.0	9.1
3.	<i>m</i> -Cl	195°	..	9.3	9.1
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	235°	..	9.2	9.1
5.	<i>o</i> -Br	95°	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ BrS	8.3	8.1
6.	<i>o</i> -Me	175°	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ S	9.7	9.6
7.	3:4-Me ₂	216°	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ S	9.1	9.3
8.	2:4-Me ₂	231°	..	9.5	9.3
9.	2:5-Me ₂	272°	..	9.2	9.3

TABLE VI

No.	Compounds, (R=)	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>o</i> -Cl	110°	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ ON ₂ CS	13.3	13.1
2.	<i>p</i> -Cl	211°	..	13.0	13.1
3.	<i>o</i> -Me	112°	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S	14.2	14.3
4.	2:4-Me ₂	114°	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ ON ₂ S	13.7	13.5
5.	2:5-Me ₂	135°	..	13.4	13.5

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